

Direct Glycosidation of Ribose in Apolar Organic Solvent and Remarkable Selectivity of a Synthetic Macrocycle for Sugars

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Sugars in aqueous solutions are solubilised in CCl_4 via complex formation with resorcinol-dodecanal cyclooligomer (**1**) as a lipophilic polar host. New synthetic reactions of sugars, especially glycoside formation in apolar organic solvents have been studied using cyclotetramer as a host solubiliser. The host acts as an acid and protonates the bound sugar in this reaction. The host **1** as the first sugar binder is shown to possess a very high selectivity for such sugars that accommodate the furanose structures. The affinities of the sugars to **1** decrease in the following order: 2-deoxy-ribose and ribose > erythrose and arabinose > glucose and mannose > xylose and lyxose. The selectivity in the present sugar-host interaction can be correlated with the two structural characteristics of a sugar, the ring size and the presence or absence of an exocyclic CH_2OH .

RECOGNITION of nonionic polar moieties through hydrogen bonding interactions constitutes an important challenge in the molecular recognition but still remains largely unexplored¹. Resorcinol-acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde cyclotetramers have long been known². They are scarcely soluble in apolar organic solvents. Acid-catalysed condensation of resorcinol and dodecanal in ethanol affords the cyclotetramer (**1**) in good yield³. It is highly soluble in apolar organic solvents such as CCl_4 and benzene. The cyclotetramer (**1**) as a lipophilic polar host solubilises glycerol and water (neat liquids) and ribose (in an aqueous solution) as polar guests in CCl_4 upon formation of monomeric complexes $1.4(\text{glycerol})$, $1.4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $1.(\text{ribose}).2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where ribose is bound highly selectively in the α -pyranose form. The ^1H nmr spectrum for the ribose complex indicates that the ribose C-H protons are considerably upfield shifted due to the ring current effect of the benzene rings of **1**. Similar extraction studies using various aldopentoses indicate a remarkable selectivity in the present sugar binding with **1**.

1: $\text{R}=(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{CH}_2$

These studies are applicable for the development of synthetic reactions of sugars, specially glycoside formation with various aglycones, in organic solvents using the present host as a solubiliser. Because **1** shows high affinities to ribose, 2-deoxy-ribose and furanosides (glycosides having the furanose rings) in general, so it is quite significant in

view of potential applications to the preparation and the separation of nucleosides containing nitrogen-glycosides of the furanose form of ribose or 2-deoxyribose, i.e. ribo- or 2-deoxyribofuranosides.

Results and Discussion

The ^1H nmr (Fig. 1) and ^{13}C nmr (Fig. 2A) of **1** in CDCl_3 indicate that the four benzene rings and four methine groups are equivalent. The OH proton resonance appeared as two singlets of equal intensities at δ_{H} 9.60 and 9.28 and disappeared on deuteration with D_2O . The ir spectrum of **1** ($1 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$ in CCl_4) showed ν_{OH} at 3250 cm^{-1} .

A pair of hydrogen bonded OH groups on adjacent benzene rings in **1** provide the essential binding site for a guest OH group. While glycerol and H_2O are singly bound with such a binding site via hydrogen bonding, α -ribopyranose is doubly bonded with two binding sites separated by a meta-phenylene bridge (Scheme 1, D-ribose). Examination of CPK molecular models indicates that such a two point 1-guest interaction is possible when six-membered ring of a guest has *cis*-OH groups on 1-C and 4-C, as in the case of α -ribopyranose.

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hydrogen bonded binding sites of host **1**

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

The ^{13}C nmr spectrum of the ribose complex 1.(ribose). $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for a CDCl_3 solution under complete proton decoupling conditions (Fig. 2B) shows the sugar carbon resonances, which are reproduced in Fig. 3, at δ_{C} 93.8, 71.7, 68.1, 67.8, and 65.0; this clearly indicates that ribose bound takes the pyranose form. The ^1H nmr spectrum for a CDCl_3 solution (Fig. 4) gives a complicated pattern. The marked signals at δ_{H} 3.21 and lower fields have an integration of 8H. This study is greatly applicable to the glycosidation reactions of sugars in organic solvents using the present host as a solubiliser.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

In the general procedure of glycosidation of sugar, the carbonyl group of aldoses and ketoses react externally under acid catalysis with alcohols to form glycosides (mixed monocyclic acetals), and under special conditions to form acyclic acetals^{4,5}. The present newly developed procedure of glycosidation reaction is very interesting in that (i) the reaction is carried out in apolar organic solvents, and the (ii) host not only solubilises the sugar, but also acts as an acid.

The general traditional procedure of glycosidation of sugar involves reaction of sugar in alcohol and in the presence of dry HCl. The mechanism involves protonation of hemiacetal hydroxyl group, removal of H_2O to give the oxocarbenium ion, followed by its capture by the solvent alcohol⁶.

Fig. 5. (A) Obtained sample of methylribofuranoside, and (B) authentic methylribofuranoside.

In our new procedure using ribose solubilised in CCl_4 by the host, the reaction mechanism was thought to be same as in the traditional method (Scheme 1). The host acts as an acid and protonates the bound sugar with the removal of H_2O and oxocarbenium ion is formed. This oxocarbenium ion is captured by alcohol. The reaction is not affected by the concentration of alcohol, e.g. 10-, 20-, 100-fold etc. while keeping the reaction time constant. The ^{13}C nmr spectrum (Fig. 5A) of the compound obtained after 24 h for a CDCl_3 solution shows marked signal at δ_{C} 107.82, which is in agreement with the furanoside form of the glycoside (Fig. 5B).

Scheme 1

It is clear from the nmr spectra that the furanosides appear to be formed in the early stage of the reaction but their quantity decreases in the later stages. On the other hand, the proportion of pyranosides increases progressively with time (Fig. 6). It is usually considered that the glycosidic linkage is stable but some cases of hydrolysis of ethyl glycosides have been observed. The reaction is thought to be applicable to any alcohol including long chain ones.

Depending on their affinities to 1, the sugars are arranged into four groups. Group 1 includes high-

affinity sugars such as 2-deoxyribose and ribose. Moderate-affinity sugars such as erythrose and arabinose constitute group 2. Group 3 includes low-affinity sugars such as glucose and mannose. In

Fig. 6. Composition of solution during riboglycoside formation at 25° : (---) pyranoside, and (···) furanoside.

group 4 are included xylose and lyxose which show almost no affinity under the present conditions. The selectivity in the present sugar-host interaction can be correlated with the two structural characteristics of a sugar, the ring size and the presence or absence of an exocyclic CH_2OH , furanose (five-membered) with an CH_2OH group > furanose without CH_2OH group > pyranose with an CH_2OH group > pyranose without CH_2OH group.

The extractabilities of various sugars were evaluated under the conditions of $1 \text{ CCl}_4 = 0.9 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[\text{sugar}]_{\text{aq}} = 2.4 M$; the sugar/1 molar ratios are shown in Fig. 7 together with the Fisher projection formulas of the sugars.

Fig. 7. Sugar/1 molar ratio: (1) Erythrose, (2) 2-deoxyribose, (3) ribose, (4) arabinose, (5) xylose, (6) lyxose, (7) glucose, (8) mannose.

Experimental

General : ^1H nmr spectra (270 MHz) were taken in D_2O , CDCl_3 or $\text{CDCl}_3 - \text{CCl}_4$ and ^{13}C nmr spectra (68.7 MHz) in CDCl_3 or D_2O on a JEOL-JNM 270 spectrometer. HPLC analysis of sugars was carried out with a JASCO apparatus equipped with an 830 RI detector on a μ -bondapak CH (Waters) or PA-03 (Yamamura Chemical Research) using H_2O or $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as eluant.

Macrocyclic host : To a solution of resorcinol (25.6 g, 0.23 mol) and dodecanal (42.8 g, 0.23 mol) in ethanol (230 ml) was added 12*N* HCl (37 ml) at 0° . The mixture was stirred at 70° under N_2 -atmosphere for 10 h. On cooling the mixture at room temperature, the resulting pale yellow precipitate was washed thoroughly with hot water (80° , 10 dm^3), dried and recrystallised twice with methanol and then twice with hexane-methanol. It was finally dried at 0.2 mm/Hg at 60° for 30 h to give compound **1** as a monohydrate as colorless needles (44.6 g ; 70%), m.p. $270 - 71^\circ$.

Ribose complex : A two phase mixture of a CCl_4 solution of **1** ($1 - 2 \times 10^{-2} M$; 100 ml) and an aqueous solution of D-ribose (5.5 *M*; 10 ml) was stirred at 20° for 24 h. The organic layer was separated, centrifuged and filtered to give a clear solution of **1**.(ribose). $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Involvement of two additional water molecules was suggested by ^1H nmr spectroscopy. Molecular weight by VPO for a CCl_4 solution was 1272 (calcd. for **1**.(ribose). $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 1292). After evaporation and drying under reduced pressure at 50° for 20 h, the dry ribose complex showed a molecular weight (3866) corresponding to a trimer (calcd. for 3(**1**.(ribose)) : 3786).

Glycoside : To a solution of ribose complex (1 g) in double-distilled CCl_4 (100 ml), double-distilled

alcohol (of different folds) was added at room temperature. The mixture was stirred in a tightly closed condition at room temperature. The sample (15 ml) was then taken out and stirred with water (10 ml) for back-extraction. The water layer was separated and centrifuged, clear water solution was pipetted out, and after evaporation and drying, the final product was obtained. Typical time required for the complete process was of the order of 72 h. However, as mentioned earlier, the reaction seemed to be highly dependent on time factor.

Competitive extraction of sugars : Two different sugars, i.e. D-ribose (1.6 *M*) and D-xylose (1.6 *M*) was stirred with a CCl_4 solution of **1** ($0.9 \times 10^{-2} M$). The organic phase was then separated and reextracted with H_2O . Hplc analysis of the H_2O extract on a column of PA-03 with $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (83 : 17 ; 1.7 ml min^{-1}) as eluant indicated that almost exclusive extraction of ribose had taken place with molar ratios, ribose/**1**=0.3 and xylose/**1**=0 ; retention times were 5.5 and 7.3 min for ribose and xylose, respectively. Other competitive extraction runs were carried out similarly. Sugars used in the experiment were commercial products.

References

1. A. G. S. HÖGGERG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 6046; H. ERDTMAN, S. HÖGGERG, S. ABRAHAMSSON and B. NILSSON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 1679; C. D. GUTSCHE and K. C. NAM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 6153.
2. J. REBEK, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 2426; A. G. S. HÖGGERG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 4498.
3. AOYAMA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 634.
4. L. D. HAYWARD and S. J. ANGYAL, *Carbohydr Res.*, 1977, **53**, 13; "Carbohydrate", ed. P. M. COLLINS, Chapman and Hall, New York, 1987.
5. A. THOMPSON in "The Carbohydrates", ed. W. PIGMAN, Academic, New York, 1957, Chap. IV.